

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Thiosemicarbazide by Potassium Bromate in Aqueous Sulphuric Acid and Water-Acetic Acid Media

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The oxidation kinetics of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) with potassium bromate in aqueous sulphuric acid and water-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) media have been studied under varying conditions. The rates of reactions show first order kinetics in [oxidant] in both the media, but show different behaviour in [TSC] and [H⁺]. The rate shows fractional order kinetics in [TSC] and nearly 1.5 order in [H⁺] in aqueous medium, compared to first order dependence in [TSC] and fractional order in [H⁺] observed in water-acetic acid. Addition of KBr, the reduced product of the oxidant has no significant effect on the rate of oxidation, while increase in ionic strength of the medium decreases the rate in both the cases. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by increasing the acetic acid composition of the solvent increases the rate. Suitable mechanisms consistent with the observed results have been considered and the related rate laws deduced. Coefficients of the rate limiting steps have been calculated at different temperatures and the related Arrhenius expressions deduced. The validity of rate laws have also been tested by recalculating the rate constants from the deduced rate law as [TSC] and [H⁺] varied. A good agreement between the recalculated values and the experimental constants provides support to the proposed mechanisms.

The chemistry of hydrazine derivatives is of importance due to their wide synthetic and analytical applications and biological activities¹. Although thiosemicarbazide (TSC) has been extensively used in synthetic organic chemistry and as a metal chelating agent², there are no reports except our recent work on the mechanistic aspects of its reactions in solution³⁻⁶. As a part of these studies we report herein the oxidation kinetics of thiosemicarbazide with acid bromate in aqueous and water-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) media in presence of sulphuric acid.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation kinetics of thiosemicarbazide with potassium bromate in aqueous sulphuric acid and water-acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) media have been studied under varying conditions. The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2 and Figs. 1 and 2.

Oxidation in aqueous sulphuric acid medium: At fixed [H₂SO₄] and with multifold excess of [TSC], the first order plots of log [KBrO₃]₀ / [KBrO₃] vs time were linear for at least two half-lives. The rate constants computed from the plots were almost unaffected by changes in [KBrO₃]₀, indicating first order kinetics in [KBrO₃]. At constant [H₂SO₄] and [KBrO₃], the rate increased with increase in [TSC] with a fractional order dependence (Table 1). The double reciprocal plot of *k*_{obs} vs [TSC] was linear (Fig. 1). The rate of oxidation showed positive dependence in [H₂SO₄]. pH of solutions were measured at different [H₂SO₄] and the effective [H⁺] were calculated. The rate showed almost the same order of dependence in [H⁺]_{eff}. The plot of 1/*k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺]² was linear (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plots of (i) $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{TSC}]_0$ ($[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and (ii) $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ ($[\text{TSC}]_0=0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$); $10^3[\text{KBrO}_3]_0=1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, medium : aqueous, temp = 303 K.

The rate decreased with increase in ionic strength of the medium (Table 1). Addition of KBr, the reduced product of the oxidant had negligible effect on the rate of oxidation.

Mechanism: The observed kinetics of first order in [oxidant], fractional order in [TSC], nearly 1.5 order in [H⁺] and non-influence of added reduced product of the oxidant on the rate, for oxidation of TSC by acid bromate may be explained by a Michaelis-Menten type mechanism shown in Scheme 1. The active species in this mechanism is H₂BrO₃⁺ as is evident from the observed kinetics in [H⁺].

Scheme 1

Based on Scheme 1, the rate laws (2-5) have been deduced.

$$-\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{oxidant}]_{\text{tot}} [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{\{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2\} [\text{H}_2\text{O}] + K_1 K_2 [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]^2} \\ &= \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{oxidant}]_{\text{tot}} [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K'_2 [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

where $K'_2 = K_2/[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$

$$\text{or} \quad k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 K'_2 [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{H}^+]^2} \left[\frac{1}{[\text{TSC}]} + \frac{1}{k_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}]} \left[\frac{1}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{1 + K'_2 [\text{TSC}]}{K_2 k_3 [\text{TSC}]} \right] \quad (5)$$

The rate laws (4 and 5) are consistent with the observed linearities between $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{TSC}]$ at constant $[\text{H}^+]$, and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ at constant $[\text{TSC}]$ (Fig. 1), with finite intercepts on the ordinates. The constant k_3 was calculated from the intercept of the plot, $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{TSC}]$ and inserting $[\text{H}_2\text{O}] = 55.506 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Further, $[\text{TSC}]$ was varied at different temperatures (298-313 K) and the values of k_3 were calculated at each temperature: $10^4 k_3 (\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}) = 2.15, 3.13, 4.65$ and 6.55 at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K respectively. These values may be represented by the Arrhenius expression,

$$k_3 = 10^{5.48} \exp(-0.33) \exp\left(-\frac{57.9 \pm 2.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}{RT}\right)$$

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{obs} FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (TSC) BY POTASSIUM BROMATE IN AQUEOUS SULPHURIC ACID ($\mu = 0.30 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, TEMP. = 303 K) AND WATER-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) ($\mu = 0.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, TEMP. = 293 K) MEDIA

Aqueous					H ₂ O-HOAc (1 : 1, v/v)				
$10^3 [\text{KBrO}_3]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2 [\text{TSC}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^1 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	pH	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$10^3 [\text{KBrO}_3]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^2 [\text{TSC}]_0$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^1 [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ mol dm ⁻³	pH	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$
[Oxidant]₀ variation									
0.20	1.0	2.0	1.58	4.4	0.20	1.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	16.3(12.0)
0.50	1.0	2.0	1.58	4.4	0.50	1.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	16.3(12.0)
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	4.1	1.0	1.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	16.3(11.2)
2.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	3.8	2.0	1.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	14.8(—)
[Substrate]₀ variation									
1.0	0.50	2.0	1.58	2.3	1.0	0.50	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	8.2(5.2)
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	4.0	1.0	1.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	16.3(11.1)
1.0	2.0	2.0	1.58	6.1	1.0	2.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	31.1(20.9)
1.0	5.0	2.0	1.58	10.6	1.0	4.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	63.5(—)
[H₂SO₄]₀ variation									
1.0	1.0	0.50	2.10	0.60	1.0	1.0	3.0(0.2)	1.91(2.31)	12.7(9.5)
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.84	1.6	1.0	1.0	4.0(0.5)	1.79(2.24)	14.3(10.3)
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	4.0	1.0	1.0	5.0(1.0)	1.68(2.13)	16.3(11.1)
1.0	1.0	3.0	1.43	6.3	1.0	1.0	7.0(2.0)	1.58(2.04)	17.8(12.1)
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	4.3 ^a	1.0	1.0	5.0	1.68	16.7 ^a
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	8.7 ^b	1.0	1.0	5.0	1.68	33.2 ^c
1.0	1.0	2.0	1.58	2.7 ^d	1.0	1.0	5.0	1.68	10.8 ^d
					1.0	1.0	5.0	1.68	6.8 ^e
					1.0	1.0	5.0	1.68	37.1 ^f

^aIn presence of 0.02 mol dm⁻³ KBr. With $\mu =$ ^b0.10; ^c0.30; ^d0.60. %AcOH = ^e25; ^f70.

The equilibrium constant K_2 was calculated from the intercept, $\{1+K_2[\text{TSC}]\}/K_2k_3[\text{TSC}]$ of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ plot by inserting k_3 , $[\text{TSC}]$ and $[\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ values, $K_2=7511$. Further, constant K_1 was calculated from the slope of either of the two plots by inserting K_2 , k_3 and $[\text{H}^+]$ or $[\text{TSC}]$ values, K_1 ($\text{dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2}$)=407.

The computed constants K_1 , K_2 and k_3 were employed to verify the rate constants from the rate law (4) or (5) as $[\text{TSC}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ varied. The recalculated values compared with the observed rate constants (k_{obs}) are shown in Table 2. A good agreement between the two sets of values checks the consistency of the rate law and thus provides support to the proposed mechanism.

Oxidation in water-acetic acid medium: Oxidation of thiosemicarbazide in aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v) also showed first order kinetics in $[\text{KBrO}_3]$, but it showed different behaviour in $[\text{TSC}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$. The rate showed first order kinetics in $[\text{TSC}]$ and fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$ as compared to fractional order kinetics in $[\text{TSC}]$ and >1 order in $[\text{H}^+]$ observed in aqueous medium. The rate decreased with increase in ionic strength of the medium, while it increased with increase in acetic acid composition of the solvent. Addition of KBr had little positive effect.

The rates were measured at different temperatures by varying [substrate] at each temperature and the coefficients of the rate limiting steps have been calculated at each temperature as described under discussion. The activation parameters corresponding to the latter constants were computed from the Arrhenius and Eyring plots.

The rate of oxidation under these conditions showed first order dependence each in [oxidant] and $[\text{TSC}]$ and fractional order in $[\text{H}^+]$ as compared to kinetics observed in aqueous medium. The reaction in aqueous acetic acid was carried out in the presence of 0.20 mol dm^{-3} sodium acetate.

Hence under these conditions, effective $[\text{H}^+]$ would be much smaller than that in aqueous medium, for comparable $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$. Therefore, HBrO_3 is likely to be the reactive species. Scheme 2 explains the observed results.

Scheme 2

The rate laws (6–8) are in accordance with Scheme 2.

$$-\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [\text{oxidant}]_{\text{tot}} [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_4 [\text{H}^+]} \quad (6)$$

or

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{K_4 k_5 [\text{TSC}] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_4 [\text{H}^+]} \quad (7)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \left\{ \frac{1}{k_5 [\text{H}^+]} + 1 \right\} \frac{1}{K_4 [\text{TSC}]} \quad (8)$$

The rate laws (7 and 8) predict linearities between k_{obs} and $[\text{TSC}]$, and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ and $1/[\text{H}^+]$. The plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{TSC}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ were linear (Fig. 2) in conformity with the predictions. The ratio of intercept to slope of the latter plot gave K_4 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)=72.3, k_5 was calculated from the intercept of the plot by inserting $[\text{TSC}]$, k_5 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)=0.27.

The rate constant for the oxidation of TSC in aqueous acetic acid may be represented by the Arrhenius relationship,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = 10^{7.23} \pm 0.52 \cdot \exp \left(-\frac{56.2 \pm 3.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}}{RT} \right) \quad (9)$$

The entropies and free energies of activation for the oxidation of TSC in aqueous and water-acetic

TABLE 2—KINETIC DATA AND COMPARISON OF RECALCULATED AND EXPERIMENTAL RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (TSC) BY POTASSIUM BROMATE IN AQUEOUS SULPHURIC ACID AND WATER-ACETIC ACID (1 : 1, v/v) MEDIA

Orders observed in	Aqueous		$\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{HOAc}$		$10^2[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}		$10^4 k$ (s^{-1}) Aqueous	
	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.
$[\text{KBrO}_3]$	1.0		1.0		0.5		0.57	0.57
$[\text{TSC}]$	0.6		1.0		1.0		1.7	1.6
$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$	1.4		0.36		2.0		4.0	4.0
$[\text{H}^+]$	1.5		0.38		3.0		5.7	6.3
	$10^4 k$ (s^{-1})							
	Aqueous		$\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{HOAc}$					
$10^3[\text{TSC}]$ mol dm^{-3}	Recalcd.	Expt.	Recalcd.	Expt.				
0.50	2.2	2.3	8.1	8.2				
1.0	4.0	4.0	16.3	16.3				
2.0	6.5	6.1	32.5	31.1				
4.0	—	—	65.0	63.5				
5.0	10.4	10.6	—	—				

acid media are : ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol⁻¹)=54.2 (Aq.), 54.1 (H₂O-HOAc) ; ΔS^\ddagger (JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹) = -152.5 (Aq.), -113.6 (H₂O-HOAc) ; ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol⁻¹)=100.4 (Aq.), 87.4 (H₂O-HOAc). Relatively high positive values for free energy of activation may signal bond breaking in the formation of transition state. Larger negative values of entropy of activation indicate that the more ordered activated complexes are formed. Change of medium from aqueous to aqueous acetic acid has not changed the energy of activation while the entropy of activation is less negative in the latter medium.

Fig. 2. Plots of (i) k_{obs} vs $[TSC]_0$ ($10^2[H_2SO_4]$)=(a) 1.0, (b) 5.0 mol dm⁻³ ; and (ii) $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[H^+]$ ($[TSC]_0 = 0.01$ mol dm⁻³) ; $10^3[KBrO_3]_0 = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, medium : H₂O-HOAc, temp. =293 K.

Several approaches have been put forward to explain quantitatively the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the rates of ion-ion, ion-dipolar molecule and dipolar molecule-dipolar molecule reactions in the liquid phase^{4,5}. The observed increase of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (effected by increasing the acetic acid composition of the solvent) may be explained by the Laidler-Eyring equation⁵,

$$\log k_D = \log k_\infty + \frac{Z^2e^2}{2Dk_B T} \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r^\ddagger} \right)$$

where r and r^\ddagger refer to the radii of the reactant species and the activated complex, respectively. It

may be seen that the rate should be greater in a medium of lower dielectric constant when $r^\ddagger > r$. It is likely that the radius of the activated complex in the present case is greater than the reactant molecules, as it will be bulkier.

Experimental

Analytical grade potassium bromate was used and its aqueous solution standardised before use. Thiosemicarbazide (E. Merck) was purified by recrystallisation from water and its aqueous stock solution (0.10 mol dm⁻³) was employed. The ionic strength of the media were maintained at 0.30 and 0.50 mol dm⁻³ in aqueous and water-acetic acid media, respectively, using concentrated aqueous solution of sodium sulphate.

In aqueous acetic acid, reactions were studied in the presence of sodium acetate (0.20 mol dm⁻³). All other reagents were of accepted grades of purity.

The kinetic studies were made in glass stoppered pyrex tubes under pseudo-first order conditions with $[substrate] \gg [oxidant]$ (5 to 50 fold excess). The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of requisite amounts of oxidant solution (0.0002–0.002 mol dm⁻³), thermally pre-equilibrated at a desired temperature, to solutions containing known amounts of the substrate (0.005–0.05 mol dm⁻³), acid (0.002–0.07 mol dm⁻³), and water (and acetic acid to maintain 1 : 1, v/v water-acetic acid) thermostated at the same temperature. The progress of the reactions was monitored for at least two half-lives by the iodometric estimation of unreacted bromate at regular intervals of time. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$ error.

The stoichiometry of bromate-TSC reaction was determined by equilibrating varying ratios of substrate and oxidant in both aqueous and water-acetic acid media in presence of sulphuric acid. TSC was found to get oxidised to sulphate to an extent of about $92 \pm 4\%$. The observed 3 : 4 molar stoichiometry may be represented by equation (1),

The presence of hydrazine in the reaction products were confirmed by its reaction with aldehydes⁶. Addition of benzaldehyde to the reaction products resulted in the separation of yellow coloured crystals of benzaldehyde azine. The other products of oxidation were identified by standard tests⁷.

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